

STUDIES IN GLYCOLIC TITRATION. PART III. TITRATION OF ORGANIC BASES AND POLYAMIDES IN GLYCOL-PHENOL MEDIUM

BY SANTI R. PALIT AND U. N. SINGH

Phenol as a co-solvent in the glycolic titrations of organic bases has been investigated and as expected from its protogenic nature, it considerably enhances the sharpness of the potentiometric end-point. A visual titration of nylon against hydrochloric acid in phenol-ethyleneglycol mixture has also been successfully carried out, using Thymol blue as indicator. The value for the molecular weight, as obtained from the method, is found to be of the right order of magnitude.

Glycolic titrations, developed by Palit (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 246) and Das and Palit (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 34, 39) where either a pure glycol mixture with a suitable co-solvent like isopropyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol or chloroform is used as a titration medium, are now well recognised and are applied for various types of titrations involving weak bases. The usual efficacy of glycols is attributed by Palit ("Non-aqueous Titration" by Palit, Das and Somayajulu, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta) to its strong hydrogen-bonding power making them virtual acids, and it is, hence, expected that phenol, which is an acid and also a good solvent for hydrocarbons, would be a good co-solvent for the purpose of the above titrations, all the more so, as phenol has also some glycolic properties. The present paper reports the behaviour of phenol as a co solvent in glycolic titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

All solvents used were purified by distillation. Details of preparation of the acid, standardisation of the same and the procedure for titration were the same as described in the monograph by Palit, Das and Somayajulu (*loc. cit.*). A Cambridge bench pattern p_H -meter was used.

Ethyleneglycol-phenol Media

Titration of Pyridine against Hydrochloric Acid.—The results of the potentiometric titrations of pyridine, a typical weak base, against hydrochloric acid in glycolic mixtures of ethyleneglycol and phenol in varying relative proportions are represented in Fig. 1. Addition of phenol in accordance with our expectation is found to bring about a remarkable increase in sharpness of the inflexion point even with 10% phenol. The enhancement of the sharpness of end-point steadily goes ahead with further addition of the co-solvent (phenol) until it reaches its maximum value with a glycolic mixture containing about 25 to 50% phenol. Further addition is not found to add much to the sharpness of the potentiometric break which is clearly demonstrated by the curve G, based on the titration of pyridine in a glycolic mixture with 66% phenol.

FIG. 1

Hence, it appears that a mixture of ethylene-glycol and phenol in the ratio of 3 : 1 to 1 : 1 can be advantageously adopted as a medium for the titration of weak bases. The use of a higher proportion of phenol, though may not have any disagreeable effect on the sharpness of the inflexion point in the curve, is not desirable in view of its corrosive nature and repulsive odour, except in special cases where some other property like its solvent action as in the case of polyamides, to be referred to later, is also of equal significance.

FIG. 2

A—Aniline vs. HCl in pure eth. glycol.
 B—Do Do Do eth glycol phenol (1:1).
 C—Pyridine vs. HCl in eth glycol-phenol (1:1) + 5% water.
 D—Nylon Do Do Do Do (1:1).

Titration of Aniline against Hydrochloric Acid.—Another weak base of slightly different type, viz., aniline, was subjected to glycolic titrations in glycol-phenol mixtures. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 2. Quite unexpectedly, however, phenol does not seem to have any appreciable effect on the sharpness of the inflexion point. This, once again, brings out in bold relief the point observed by us earlier that the relative basicity in organic solvents may be quite different from that in water. It appears that the explanation has to be sought in some latent power of phenol to partly shield off the basicity of aniline, but not of pyridine.

Titrations against Perchloric Acid.—In view of a difference in the behaviour of HCl and HClO₄ in non-aqueous solvents, as reported by Palit *et al.* (Monograph) a few titrations of pyridine and aniline in pure ethyleneglycol and in a glycol-phenol mixture (1:1) have been carried out and the results are represented in Fig. 3. Perchloric acid behaves as a much stronger acid as compared to HCl in glycol-phenol mixture and the solution resembles the "super acid solution" of Conant and Hall in glacial acetic acid. Even with a small concentration of the acid, the p_x of the solution extends below 0 on the usual p_H scale of a glass electrode p_H -meter. To obtain the reading in the conventional manner with the p_H -meter, the p_H -meter was set one p_x unit higher than the true p_H of the standardising buffer, which was subsequently subtracted from the observed values.

FIG. 3

- A—Pyridine vs. perchloric acid in pure eth.glycol.
 B— Do " " eth.glycol-phenol (1:1).
 C—Aniline " " pure eth. glycol.
 D— Do " " eth.glycol-phenol (1:1).

In pure ethyleneglycol, the perchloric acid does not seem to bring about much improvement in the inflexion point over hydrochloric acid, as shown by curves A

and C in Fig. 3. Addition of phenol greatly enhances the sharpness of the potentiometric break in the titration of pyridine, as shown by the curve B in Fig. 3. In the case of aniline, though a slight improvement is observed, it is not of the order as noticed in the titration of pyridine. Thus, it appears from the titrations of aniline against HCl as well as against HClO_4 , that phenol does not add much to the sharpness of the inflexion point as it does to a reasonable extent in the case of a heterocyclic bases, like pyridine. It thus appears that glycol-phenol mixtures are specially suited for the titration of weak heterocyclic bases.

Differential Titrations.—The following pairs of bases were successfully titrated differentially in glycol-phenol media: (i) diethylamine and pyridine, (ii) triethylamine and pyridine and (iii) ammonia and pyridine. The potentiometric titration curves are shown in Fig. 4. It would be noticed that sharp differential titrations are possible and also that the three curves are practically identical despite a considerably low value for the basicity of triethylamine ($pK-3.19$) and ammonia ($pK-4.76$) as compared to diethylamine ($pK-2.90$) in aqueous medium. In the same graph a differential titration curve between aniline and triethylamine is also included. It thus appears that aniline can be differentially estimated with precision if present in mixture with any alkylamine. However, in a mixture of aniline and pyridine or in a mixture of two alkylamines, say diethylamine and ammonia (or tributylamine) the individual bases cannot be estimated by differential titrations.

FIG. 4

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| A—Diethylamine + pyridine. | B—Triethylamine + pyridine. |
| C—Ammonia + pyridine. | D—Triethylamine + aniline. |
| E—Ammonia + pyridine in water. | F—Na-acetate + pyridine. |
| G—Diethylamine + Na-acetate. | |

Quite unexpectedly, however, sodium acetate, which is undoubtedly one of the strongest bases in glycolic media, so much so that it can be titrated with indicators with extreme accuracy, could not be differentially titrated from pyridine or for that matter from any organic base.

Reproducibility and Accuracy.—Glycolic titrations, as we have also pointed out before, have the unique advantage that ordinary glass electrodes can be used and the potentials are highly reproducible and stable. In this respect, the method possesses a special advantage over the alternative method of titration in glacial acetic acid, which latter requires special electrodes and often the potentials are unstable and non-reproducible (Warner and Haskel, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 770).

Even a trace of water has a deleterious effect with most of the weak organic bases by indicator method in glacial acetic acid. However, in the present method presence of water up to a concentration near about 5% is not harmful, and end-points can be detected with indicators, as also by potentiometry. A typical titration curve for pyridine in the glycolic mixture (ethyleneglycol: phenol = 1:1) containing 5% of water has been represented in Fig. 2 by the curve C in support of our above statement.

Titration of Polyamides.—A potentiometric titration of nylon (polyhexamethylenediammonium adipate) in phenol-propyleneglycol mixture has been reported by Basu from this laboratory (*J. Polymer Sci.*, 1950, **5**, 735) which, however, involves considerable practical difficulties due to its very low solubility in the above solvent mixture. An attempt has been made by the present authors to carry on a visual titration using Thymol blue as an indicator at a moderately high temperature (70°) so as to keep nylon in solution. On adding a few drops of Thymol blue to the phenolic solution, an orange or a slightly reddish colour appears due to the inherent acidity of the solvent (phenol). Addition of a few c. c. of ethyleneglycol restores the characteristic yellow colour by lowering down the acidity of the solution and thus brings it in the working range of the indicator (Thymol blue). It was titrated against hydrochloric acid, dissolved in a phenol-glycol mixture. Though the end-point is not so sharp, because of the simplicity and quickness of the method it may be recommended in the routine analysis for controlling the quality of nylon which invariably depends upon its molecular weight. With a particular sample of nylon, considering it to be a monoacidic base, we obtained its molecular weight to be 10,494 and 10,714 (mean 10,600) respectively in two titrations against *M/20*-HCl using Thymol blue as an indicator. This value of the molecular weight seems to be of the right order of magnitude for the commercial nylon.

Nylon salt (hexamethylenediammonium adipate) behaves as a very strong base in the solvent, as shown by the titration curve D in Fig. 2. Visual titration, using Thymol blue as indicator too, gave excellent results with a very sharp colour change.

Out of the several indicators tested for their working in phenol-glycolic media, Thymol blue and Dimethyl yellow showed colour change from yellow to red. However, the change in both the cases is not sharp and becomes still more sluggish with an increased proportion of phenol.

DISCUSSION

Addition of phenol to ethyleneglycol, besides its remarkable effect in enhancing the sharpness of the potentiometric end-point, brings about a "downwards stretching" of the lower parts of the titration curves, as is evident from Fig. 1. It is evidently due to the presence of the highly protogenic $C_6H_5OH_2^+$ ion in the solution, formed by the proton-transfer reaction between the free acid and the phenol molecule, *i.e.*

The neutralisation p_H is also lowered down by the addition of phenol, as is clearly seen from the family of curves in Fig. 1. The following table represents the neutralisation p_H for pyridine in the ethyleneglycol-phenol mixture with varying proportions of phenol.

TABLE I

% Phenol	0	10	25	33	50	water
Neutralisation p_H	1.85	1.75	1.70	1.45	1.35	3.15

In the titration of aniline and pyridine against perchloric acid, it has been observed that the apparent p_H values after the equivalence point are much lower than those obtained in the case of hydrochloric acid. It clearly shows in a qualitative way that the former is much stronger an acid than the latter in phenol.

Diethylamine, triethylamine and ammonia appear to be of nearly of the same strength in the glycol-phenol mixture (1:1) due to the levelling effect of the solvent, as is evident in a qualitative way from the neutralisation p_H values for the bases (diethylamine = 5.7, triethylamine = 5.7 and ammonia = 5.6) read from the curves A, B and C in Fig. 4.